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WAYS OF CONVEYING THE INNER EMOTIONAL STATE IN LERMONTOV'S PROSE

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Annotation: The focus of the article is upon the hypothesis is that, despite the obvious differences in Lermontov's style and language from the writers of the previous period, his descriptions of the emotional states of his characters still use a set of images characteristic of the Romantic era. Besides, we assume that his prose contains numerous examples of borrowings, first of all, from the French language. Using elements of old Slavic language included in Lermontov's prose can be called the principle of historicism, i.e. borrowing any elements of language for artistic purposes. We suggest that Lermontov's prose represents a transitional stage from Romanticism to Realism. In the language of the novel we can see features of the previous epoch (18th century) along with manifestations of already new features of 19th century prose. The main way of presenting the emotional state of the hero is the way of describing the physical actions that express this or that emotion, which is explained by the lack of means to describe the internal psychological and mental experiences.

Keywords: romanticism, literature style, prose, Lermontov, borrowings

СПОСОБЫ ПЕРЕДАЧИ ВНУТРЕННЕГО ЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ В ПРОЗЕ ЛЕРМОНТОВА

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Аннотация: В центре внимания статьи находится гипотеза о том, что, несмотря на очевидные отличия стиля и языка Лермонтова от писателей предшествующего периода, в его описаниях эмоциональных состояний своих героев все еще используется набор образов, характерный для романтизма. эпоха. Кроме того, мы предполагаем, что его проза содержит многочисленные примеры заимствований, прежде всего, из французского языка. Использование элементов старославянского языка, включенных в лермонтовскую прозу, можно назвать принципом историзма, т. е. заимствования любых элементов языка в художественных целях. Мы предполагаем, что проза Лермонтова представляет собой переходный этап от романтизма к реализму. В языке романа мы можем видеть черты предыдущей эпохи (XVIII век) наряду с проявлениями уже новых черт прозы XIX века. Основным способом представления эмоционального состояния героя является способ описания физических действий, выражающих ту или иную эмоцию, что объясняется отсутствием средств для описания внутренних психологических и психических переживаний.

Ключевые слова: романтизм, литературный стиль, проза, Лермонтов, заимствования

Mikhail Lermontov's novel "A Hero of Our Time" is considered one of the best samples of Russian prose of the 19th century. Anton Chekhov said more than once that he didn't know language better than Lermontov's: "I would do this: I would take his story and parse it, as they do at school, sentence by sentence, part by part... That's how I would learn to write..." [1, с. 455]. Other contemporaries praised the merits of the novel no less. Thus, V. G. Belinsky wrote of the novel as a lyrical poem in which it is impossible to change a single word. To retell the content, in his words, is tantamount to telling about the beauty of a woman you have not seen yourself [2]. Said very figuratively, but vaguely. Vladimir Nabokov's assessment of this novel, given in the preface to the translation, made by his son, Dmitry, is well known. Nabokov thought that Lermontov's prose was far from graceful, it was dry and monotonous, since it was in the hands of a talented but inexperienced writer. "His Russian is at times as sloppy as Stendhal's French; his comparisons and metaphors are banal; his common

epithets are saved only by the fact that they happen to be misused. The verbal repetition in his descriptive sentences cannot but annoy the purist. But he also noted that Russian realistic prose at the time was just forming, and the author was twenty-five years old, so "we can only be amazed at the exceptional energy of the narrative and the remarkable rhythm, which is felt not so much at the level of the phrase, as at the level of the paragraph" [3, с. 72]. Researchers note that Pechorin's effective, emotional, reflective character is conveyed by short, incomplete, simple sentences with lots of elliptical and question-answer forms. There are often omissions of words and incompleteness of sentences. Phrases are divided into two or three-member constructions, creating an internal rhythm, of which Nabokov wrote.

The middle of the 19th century was a time of transition from Romanticism to Realism. Lermontov continued Pushkin's tradition in prose. "The rejection of metaphor, the subject precision of word usage, the predominance of simple sentences that give a concise, succinct narrative – these are the main features of Lermontov's prose speech in "A Hero of Our Time" [4, с. 616]. At the same time, Lermontov does not abandon the achievements of Romanticism either. Where necessary, he willingly uses the system of figurative means developed by the Romanticists. However, Lermontov uses them to show more deeply and fully the complex and contradictory figure of the hero. As V.V. Vinogradov noted, in the novel "a new stylistic synthesis of the achievements of verse and prose culture of Russian speech was carried out" [5, с. 624].

Lermontov followed Pushkin in incorporating into the language what had been created in previous periods of its development, because it enriches the language, expands its stylistic possibilities and enhances its artistic expressiveness. Therefore, it is quite logical to include Slavicisms in a literary work, as they have great expressiveness. This principle of using elements of language can be called the principle of historicism, i.e. borrowing any elements of language for artistic purposes.

Let us turn directly to the subject of our consideration, namely to the ways of conveying the emotional state of the hero in Pechorin's Journal, Part 1 "Taman". Here we can distinguish several main ways:

1. Lexical repetition:

я три ночи не спал, измучился и начинал *сердиться*
Я вернулся домой угрюм и *сердит*

"Что это значит?" – сказал я *сердито*

я побранил его, *посердился*

Признаюсь, я имею сильное *предубеждение* против всех слепых, кривых, глухих, немых, безногих, безруких, горбатых и проч.

признаюсь, все эти странности меня тревожили, и я насилу дождался утра

Я часто склонен к *предубеждениям*...

но такова сила *предубеждений*: правильный нос свёл меня с ума;

Она была далеко не красавица, но я имею свои *предубеждения* также и насчёт красоты.

я с *невольным* биением сердца глядел на бедную лодку

Мне *невольно* пришло на мысль

он мне *напомнил* один из тех взглядов, которые в старые годы так самовластно играли моею жизнью

напомнил мне старые годы, перенес мои мысли на север, в нашу холодную столицу

В голове моей родилось *подозрение*

тут ужасное *подозрение* закралось мне в душу

2. The use of verbs describing an inner state of mind

Волнуемый воспоминаниями, я забылся...

но я молчал, полный неизъяснимого смущения

кровь хлынула мне в голову

Только тут я опомнился

В глазах у меня потемнело, голова закружилась

Мне стало грустно

Мне это надоело

я на минуту задумался

напрасно я старался уверить себя

3. Reaction to external factors

Here is small fragment from the novel describing the meeting between the hero and the girl:

«Она села против меня тихо и безмолвно и устремила на меня глаза свои, и не знаю почему, но этот взор показался мне чудно-нежен; он мне напомнил один из тех взглядов, которые в старые годы так самовластно играли моею жизнью. Она, казалось, ждала вопроса, но я молчал, полный неизъяснимого смущения. Лицо ее было покрыто

тусклой бледностью, изобличавшей волнение душевное; рука ее без цели бродила по столу, и я заметил на ней легкий трепет; грудь ее то высоко поднималась, то, казалось, она удерживала дыхание. Эта комедия начинала мне надоедать, и я готов был прервать молчание самым прозаическим образом, то есть предложить ей стакан чая, как вдруг она вскочила, обвила руками мою шею, и влажный, огненный поцелуй прозвучал на губах моих. В глазах у меня потемнело, голова закружилась, я сжал ее в моих объятиях со всею силою юношеской страсти, но она, как змея, скользнула между моими руками, шепнув мне на ухо: «Нынче ночью, как все уснут, выходи на берег», – и стрелой выскочила из комнаты <...> Только тут я опомнился» [6, с. 64].

It is worth paying attention to the set of words that Lermontov uses when describing this episode: *тихо и безмолвно, устремить глаза, чудно-нежен, играть жизнью, полный неизъяснимого смущения, тусклая бледность, душевное волнение, влажный, огненный поцелуй, в глазах у меня потемнело, голова закружилась, опомнился*. Most of the words describe external manifestations of feelings, primarily physical ones, since moments of mental turmoil and disruption of the usual rhythm of life are important for the portrayal of the romantic hero.

Lermontov uses the technique of psycho-physiological parallelism – "the portrayal of external manifestations of inner feelings, reading and recognizing them by the face and appearance of the person in general" [7, с. 12]. In the literature of the early 19th century a circle of stable comparisons and epithets was formed, which described the emotional state of the characters, such combinations as *томный взор, неизъяснимое волнение, безмолвный взгляд, мрачный вид, невольный стон, пылкая душа, угрюмый берег*, etc. For comparison, here is a fragment from Nikolai Karamzin's story "Poor Liza:

«Там, опершись на развалины гробных камней, внимаю глухому стону времен, бездною минувшего поглощенных, – стону, от которого сердце мое содрогается и трепещет. Там юный монах – с бледным лицом, с томным взором – смотрит в поле сквозь решетку окна, видит веселых птичек, свободно плавающих в море воздуха, видит – и проливает горькие слезы из глаз своих. Он томится, вянет, сохнет – и унылый звон колокола возвещает мне безвременную смерть его» [8, с. 1].

Such epithets abound in Stendhal's novel *The Red and the Black*: *мрачное недовольство, пламенная душа, стройный и гибкий стан, сладостное забытьё, дерзкая мысль, глубокая задумчивость, застыл от изумления, иступленная, судорожная порывистость, томительный страх, мучительное томление, лишиться рассудка, пламенное благочестие, смутная сладостная истома, она в изнеможении опустила на стул, томный взор*, etc. It was written in 1830, about the same time as Lermontov's novel. It is impossible not to pay attention to the almost verbatim repetition of the lexical ways of conveying the emotional state of the heroes through the description of its external expression, which is very characteristic of the Romantic tradition. "The Romantic poet fixes attention only on the violation of the norm of moral well-being, on the culmination of passion or the mental crisis of the hero. The ups and downs of his spirit are accompanied by increased external expression: laughter, gnashing of teeth, deathly pallor, a state of torpor, etc." [9, c. 50]. The characters pale, fall without feeling, beat their fist on the table, remain in a daze, fall without strength, in exhaustion, blush painfully, clench their hands convulsively, trembling, excited, they freeze, but we know nothing about what is happening in their soul. "The romantic verbal portrait lacks (or is weakened by) realistic concreteness and detail. It is more often than not of a plastic, but of a generalized and poetic nature, striving to convey only a general impression of the appearance of a person..." [Ibid, p. 118]. All this prepares the ground for the transition to the portrayal of genuine inner feelings of the characters, as in the works of Turgenev, Tolstoy, Dostoevsky.

Next we will trace which lexical layers Lermontov uses to achieve artistic effect. But first it is worth making an important observation. Pushkin's and Lermontov's choice of Church Slavonic or Russian expressions is based on different principles than those of his predecessors. Whereas the latter, aiming for an even style, excluded Gallicisms or Slavicisms, Lermontov follows the path of combining stylistically heterogeneous elements. For the 18th century, Slavicisms are correlated with high content, and Russisms with low content; for the 19th century, the choice is determined by the artistic task, the appropriateness of the pictorial means, and the aesthetics of the work. Slavicisms are regarded by him as a conscious poetic device, they perform an aesthetic function, and gallicisms – as neutral elements of speech. Thus, the problem of the choice between

Church Slavonic and Russian expressions becomes a problem of poetics. Lermontov's Slavisms are symbols of this or that cultural and ideological position – Latin-Polish, biblical, high style poetry, romantic poetry, etc. They act as words-quotes, as signs of literary tradition.

The following tendencies can be traced in the vocabulary of Lermontov's novel:

- 1) the use of native Russian words, often of Old Slavonic origin;
- 2) borrowings and calques.

The first group includes the following words and expressions:

1. **Томный** – **томъньи** in Old Russian – weakened, exhausted, tired. At the beginning of the 19th century the word languid develops the meaning 'full of sweet melancholy, tender and sad, expressing touching exhaustion'. The word **томный** becomes fashionable. **Томный** is a property of a sensitive nature. Cf. **Вы на меня сердитесь? Она подняла на меня томный, глубокий взор и покачала головой** [6, p. 112].

2. The word "**ворожить**" is used in Russian at the end of the twelfth century. This word is found in Russian since the end of the XII century. The Slavs called sorcerers "**ворогами**", hence the words appear «**ворожить, околдовать**». "**Околдовать**" means "**пленить,**" "**вызвать восхищение**". It is found in prose of Polevoy, Stanyukevich, Fet, Vyazemsky, Danilevsky, Tolstoy, Saltykov-Shchedrin, Grigorovich, Kuprin, i.e. in 19th century literature. In the 20th century and later there are few instances of its use (Nabokov, Tynyanov, Pelevin, Piecukh).

3. **Трепет** – a slight trembling, shaking, flickering; strong excitement, fear. It is derived from the Proto-Slavonic base, from which, among others, originated: St. Slavonic **трепеть**, Russian **трепет**, Ukr. – **трепет** the same, **трепéта** "aspen, *Populus tremula* L.", Bulgarian **трепет**, Serbohorv. **трéпéт**, Slovensk. **trepet** (Gen. -éta), Polish. "**trezpiot, upper-luz. třepjet, třerot**).

4. The word «**изобличать**» is means to show, to make manifest someone's guilt; to reveal someone's involvement in something reprehensible; to incriminate. Borrowing from Old Slavonic, where it is formed from the verb **личити** – "**изобличать**", goes back to the same base as the noun countenance (which once had the meaning "face side"). The word derived from the same base as the noun **лик** (which once had the meaning 'face side'). 'silent, mute'.

5. Безмолвный – Old.Slav., adjective, спокойный, тихий, chech. bezmluvny, adjective. 'безмолвный, немой [10].

The group of gallicisms can include such combinations as *тусклая бледность* which occurs several times in the novel itself (Princess Mary, Fatalist), in the story "Vadim". According to Nabokov, it is a Gallicism (fr. *paleur mate*), meaning matte, devoid of any shade of whiteness. Here are some other examples:

– впечатление is a 18th-century derivation of the French word impression: it corresponds to "in," presse to "seal" (from the French verb presser "to press, press, print", "ion" is a compound of the suffix "lazy" and the ending "e");

– предубеждение – is a word-formation derivative of the 18th century, French préjugé – "предубеждение";

– наклонности- is considered a derivative of the French word inclination, bow; inclination, affection;

– трогать (волновать) – semantic tracing of the late 18th century from the French word toucher – "to excite, touch".

Thus, we can conclude that Lermontov's prose represents a transitional stage from Romanticism to Realism. In the language of the novel we can see features of the previous epoch (18th century) along with manifestations of already new features of 19th century prose. The main way of presenting the emotional state of the hero is the way of describing the physical actions that express this or that emotion, which is explained by the lack of means to describe the internal psychological and mental experiences.

Bibliography

[1] Shchukin S.P. From Memoirs of Chekhov. Collection "Chekhov in Memoirs of Contemporaries," / S.P. Shchukin – 1960. 832 p.

[2] Belinsky V.G. Hero of our time. Composition of M. Lermontov. Article one. SPb, 1840 [Electronic resource] – URL: http://dugward.ru/library/lermont/belinskiy_geroy_nash_vr.html (date of access: 27.01.2023).

[3] Michail Lermontov. A Hero of Our Time. Translated from Russian by Vladimir and Dmitry Nabokov. Everyman's Library. Alfred A. Knopf. – New York. 1958. 69-81 p.

- [4] Sokolov A.N. History of Russian Literature of XIXth century (First half). / A.N. Sokolov – Moscow: High School, 1976. 638 p.
- [5] Vinogradov V.V. The style of Lermontov's prose. / V.V. Vinogradov – Literary Heritage, vol. 43-44. M., 1941. 517-628 p.
- [6] Lermontov M.Y. Collected Works in 4 volumes. / M.Y. Lermontov – Moscow. Art Literature, 1958. Vol.4.
- [7] Komarova M.A. Abstracted vocabulary expressing notions of the inner world in the prose of Lermontov M. Yu. Author's thesis. / M.A. Komarova // Candidate Dissertation... – M., 1963. 24 p.
- [8] Karamzin N.M. Essays in 2 volumes. / N.M. Karamzin – Leningrad.: Art Literature, 1984. Vol. 1.
- [9] Umanskaya M.M. Lermontov and romanticism of his time. / M.M. Umanskaya – Yaroslavl, 1971. 304 p.
- [10] Trubachev's Etymological Dictionary of Slavic Languages [Electronic resource] – URL: <http://www.proto-slavic.ru/dic-trubachev/index.html> (date of acces: 26.01.2023).

Список литературы (перевод)

- [1] Щукин С.П. Из воспоминаний Чехова. Сборник «Чехов в воспоминаниях современников» / С.П. Щукин – 1960. 832 с.
- [2] Белинский В.Г. Герой нашего времени. Композиция М. Лермонтова. Статья первая. СПб, 1840 [Электронный ресурс] – URL: http://dugward.ru/library/lermont/belinskiy_geroy_nash_vr.html (дата обращения: 27.01.2023).
- [3] Михаил Лермонтов. Герой нашего времени. Перевод с русского Владимира и Дмитрия Набоковых. Библиотека обывателя. Альфред А. Кнопф. – Нью-Йорк. 1958. 69-81 с.
- [4] Соколов А.Н. История русской литературы XIX века (первая половина). / А.Н. Соколов – Москва: Высшая школа, 1976. 638 с.
- [5] Виноградов В.В. Стиль прозы Лермонтова. / В.В. Виноградов – Литературное наследие, т. 43-44. М., 1941. 517-628 с.
- [6] Лермонтов М.Ю. Собрание сочинений в 4-х томах. / МОЙ. Лермонтов – Москва. Художественная литература, 1958. Том 4.
- [7] Комарова М.А. Абстрагированная лексика, выражающая представления о внутреннем мире в прозе Лермонтова М.Ю.

Авторская диссертация. / М.А. Комарова // Кандидатская диссертация.... – М., 1963. 24 с.

[8] Карамзин Н.М. Очерки в 2-х томах. / Карамзин Н.М. – Л.: Художественная литература, 1984. Т. 2. 1.

[9] Уманская М.М. Лермонтов и романтизм его времени. / М.М. Уманская – Ярославль, 1971. 304 с.

[10] Этимологический словарь славянских языков Трубачева [Электронный ресурс] – URL: <http://www.proto-slavic.ru/dic-trubachev/index.html> (дата обращения: 26.01.2023).

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